

54th Days of Preventive Medicine

International Congress

27-30. September 2022.

Niš, Serbia

BOOK OF ABSTRACT

Public Health Institute Niš

Faculty of Medicine,
University of Niš

Serbian Medical Society

Niš, 2022.

*122 years of Public Health Protection in Serbia
from regular preventive activities
to great challenges in COVID-19 pandemic time*

*122 године заштите јавног здравља у Србији
од редовних превентивних активности
до великих изазова у време пандемије COVID-19*

**PUBLIC HEALTH INSTITUTE NIŠ
FACULTY OF MEDICINE, UNIVERSITY OF NIŠ
SERBIAN MEDICAL SOCIETY, NIŠ**

**54TH DAYS OF PREVENTIVE MEDICINE
INTERNATIONAL CONGRESS**

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Publisher

Издавач
Public Health Institute Niš - Институт за јавно здравље Ниш
Faculty of Medicine Niš, University of Niš - Медицински факултет у Нишу, Универзитет у Нишу
Serbian Medical Society - Српско лекарско друштво

For publisher

Prof. dr Miodrag Stojanović

All abstracts are published in the book of abstracts in the form in which they were submitted by the authors, who are responsible for their content.

The continuing education program number 10 A-11229/20 was accredited by the decision of the Health Council of the Republic of Serbia No. 153-02-00473/2020-01 from 21th May 2020.

ISBN 978-86-6265-111-2

MAIN TOPICS

- **Environment and health**
- **Nutrition and health**
- **Microbiology today**
- **Current parasitosis**
- **Theoretical and practical problems of communicable diseases**
- **Theoretical and practical problems of non-communicable diseases**
- **Health promotion – challenges and solutions**
- **Preventive aspect of healthcare organization**
- **Application of information and communication tools in the health care system**

The Congress is accredited (153-02-00473/2020-01 from 21th May 2020; number 10 A-11229/20) as international by the Health Council of the Republic of Serbia with the following number of points:

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17. ATTITUDES OF MEDICAL SPECIALISTS TOWARDS NUTRITION AND NUTRITION CARE - ARE THEY ASSOCIATED WITH NUTRITION COUNSELLING PRACTICE

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Objectives: The aim of the study was to review existing literature on medical specialists' attitudes towards nutrition and nutrition care and their association with nutrition counseling practice. **Methods:** Literature search of PubMed, SCOPUS and Google Scholar databases was performed using terms and keywords relevant to the topic. **Results:** Medical specialists expressed positive attitudes towards the significance of nutrition and nutrition care in the prevention and treatment of diet-related diseases. Attitudes of specialists were no different from those of non-specialized medical doctors, nor between specialists in different areas of medicine. Favorable attitudes of medical specialists towards nutrition and nutrition care were generally positively correlated with the provision of nutrition counseling in their daily practice. However, some research suggested that, despite having positive attitudes, medical specialists did not always provide nutrition counseling to all of their patients in need. Furthermore, there were reports of frequent provision of nutrition counseling by specialists who expressed fewer positive attitudes towards nutrition as a determinant of health. **Conclusions:** In order to make the provision of nutrition counseling in medical specialists' offices more consistent, health policy creators should work to improve medical specialists' attitudes towards nutrition and nutrition care to better their patients' health outcomes.

Keywords: nutrition care; attitude; counseling; specialists